

Report on
RESULT SHARING WORKSHOPS
(Bihar, Jharkhand, West Bengal)

A Platform For Sharing Knowledge, Networking, and
Identifying Opportunities for Future Collaboration
2022-2023

Submitted to
FAO, ITPGRFA IV CYCLE PROJECT

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Under the project
Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population

Result Sharing Workshop 2 December 2022 Murti, West Bengal

Date and venue

December 2, 2022. Resort Resource Wood Point, Murthi West Bengal

Participants

Project team, resource person and lead farmers= 30.

Intervention and Discussion

After the introduction in friendly environment, Mr. Vikas Arora, National Coordinator of PAIRVI discussed about the objectives of result sharing stakeholders workshop with all participants. Then the project team shared the past activities and its impacts of the FAO supported project implemented by PAIRVI. All participants appreciated the project outcomes so far. Mutually they took decision to sustain the Community Seeds Bank (CSB) to enhance the cultivation of diversified pulse and oil seeds. It has been discussed that community led CSB formed on 16th March 2022. Now, time to re-structure it as felt by the all participants. Newly formed CSB consists of 11 members representing all five project villages of Jalpaiguri district. The progressive farmer, Mr. Jitu Lohar has been re-elected as president, Mrs. Anita Das as vice-president, Mrs. Bhaswati Roy elected as secretary, Jamuna Sharma as Cashier of the CSB. The meeting took decision that they will be conducting a monthly meeting with all members for planning and implementation of the existing project activities. They will contribute Rs. 10/- per month per member to mobilizing the fund for innovative activity to be done collectively.

Mr. Soumyajit Roy (Resource Person), Block Technology Manager of Agriculture departments discussed about governments schemes and facilities of the farming community and how to access it. All farmers appreciated and promise to communicate with agriculture department regularly. The Mr. Roy also appreciated the concept and design of the CSB. He said that he will discussed this research work with his higher authority so that pulse and oil seeds can be promoted by establishing CSB at different location of the district. He also promised to provide the technical training and exposure for the project farmers through his department. Mr. Roy also agreed to support the poor farmers in providing agriculture inputs and technologies.

Then the project team, representatives of CSB, selected farmer and block technology manager visited the CSB. Today the project also gifted a digital balance to the CSB for proper measuring of seeds. The farmers were very happy to receive it. Mr. Dhananjay Ray also discussed about farmers collective model experimented under ACIAR supported project in Coochbehar district. The farmers also agreed to adopt the farmers collective model to enhance the productivity of the pulse and oil seeds.

Workshop outcomes and follow up

The followings are the major outcomes evolved from this result sharing workshop-

- The improved relationship between farming community and the agriculture department. It will help the project farmers to access the government schemes and facilities.
- The department will plan to adopt the well tested community seeds bank (CSB) at non-project interventions area. It will help to scaling out the good results evolved from this project.
- The CSB restructured and mobilizing fund by contributing some amount by the CSB member. The digital balance will support the CSB to sustain the project activities.
- The project farmers are also willing to form the collective farming group – it will help farmers to reduce the production cost and enhance the confidence and trust among the farmers.

Annex: Participants list

1. Jitu Lohar, project farmer
2. Sampa Roy, project farmer
3. Jamuna Sharma, project farmer
4. Anju Lama, project farmer
5. Kanchi Lama, project farmer
6. Bhaleswari Roy, project farmer
7. Swapna Roy, project farmer
8. Rupali Roy, project farmer
9. Bina Roy, project farmer
10. Alo Roy, project farmer
11. Eshaful Islam, project farmer
12. Anita Das, project farmer
13. Kaliprashna Roy, project farmer
14. Dipak Roy, project farmer

15. Mayla Biswkarma, project farmer
16. Tezbahadur Sonar, project farmer
17. Prashanta Das, project farmer
18. Chome Oraon, project farmer
19. Barun Roy, project farmer
20. Masidul Islam, project farmer
21. Nabesh Roy, project farmer
22. Mithun Oraon, project farmer
23. Sahanur Islam, project farmer
24. Biren Roy, project farmer
25. Amal Roy, project farmer
26. Punai Oraon, project farmer
27. Soumyajit Roy, Resource Person
28. Mithun Roy, Project supervisor
29. Dhananjay Ray, Field coordinator
30. Viaks Arora, Coordinator

RESULT SHARING WORKSHOP

28TH April 2022 (Bihar)

29th April 2022 (Jharkhand)

Fig. Participants on 28th April 2022 (Bihar)

On April 28th and 29th Two days Result sharing workshop, 2022 was organized by the Delhi-based PARVI organization at the District Agriculture Office in Deoghar District, Jharkhand. Farmers from five villages in the Deoghar block of Jharkhand state, namely Tulsitard, Kovaadah, Manganasar, Bahroki, and Bhalsuia and six villages of Bihar participated.

Fig. Pudi Soren, Bihar Women Farmer Inaugurated the Booklet: “When Soil Shows Success”

The workshop began with a cultural welcome song performed by tribal women. Subhash Chandra Dubey then discussed the objectives of the workshop in detail. He explained that during the three-year project period of PAIRVI Delhi, farmers were motivated to use more pulses and oilseeds for sowing, resulting in more productivity. Farmers were also made aware of seed-bank techniques, as well as rules for planting their own seeds. Dubey mentioned that Subhodi Soren, a female farmer from the village of Tulsu Tola, is a highly progressive farmer who emphasizes on cultivating pulses and oilseeds. With enthusiasm this year, the area of arhar, masoor, and chana (gram) cultivation in winter sarson has been increased. The farmers have also agreed to increase the cultivation of millets, pulses and oilseeds this year compared to the previous years.

Afterward, Mr. Montu Kumar, the Deputy Project Director of the ATMA, Agriculture Department, addressed the farmers and stated that the land in Jharkhand is very useful for sowing. He explained that the soil's fertility and productivity for pulses and oilseeds cultivation decrease over time. Therefore, farmers should focus on the upper layer of soil for better yields. Kumar also focused the importance of using organic manure and fertilizers and following sustainable agricultural practices.

After that, he talked about the cultivation of lentils, moong beans, chickpeas, sesame seeds, watermelon, and peanuts, and mentioned that cultivating watermelon is very easy and doesn't require much investment. He also talked about the GNG 1958 variety of chickpeas and explained

that GNG stands for Ganga Nagi Gram, and this variety has a very good yield. He discussed the benefits of chickpeas, explaining that it starts benefiting farmers from birth as its leaves can be eaten when it's small, and when it grows, people buy it in the market at a good price. He also mentioned that RGN 258 is the best variety of mustard seeds, and gave information about PUSA PM 30 as well.

After that, he suggested farming of papaya and bananas in the field. The D 9 variety of bananas is quite beneficial. He further explained that through ATMA, farmers are sent to Bangalore for training from time to time.

Fig. Knowledge Material distributed in Workshop

Fig. Participants on 29th April 2022 (Jharkhand)

Mr. Vikas Arora, the national coordinator of the PAIRVI Delhi project, held extensive discussions with farmers regarding the management of the seed bank and the formation of a 12-member committee. He mentioned that the committee would be registered in December and efforts would be made to connect it with the cooperative department. Discussing the process of forming the committee, he mentioned that there would be three permanent members, and the selection of other members would be based on the suggestions of the farmers under PAIRVI.

Ms. Subodhi Soren, a female farmer from Tulsitand, about not depositing seeds in the seed bank, she explained that our pigeon pea crop was damaged by pests, and we couldn't deposit our seeds in the seed bank. Similarly, when he asked Ms. Makhku Hembram, a female farmer, about returning the moong seed, she replied that the pest infestation was so severe that we couldn't produce even a little moong.

Agricultural scientist Parimal Kumar Singh addressed farmers and explained that your land is very useful for growing sesame and pulses. He mentioned that the advanced farmers of Basahra village, Haremaam Yadav and Tulsitandan, cultivate sesame and pulses in an excellent manner. He further explained that farming sesame and pulses can also increase the fertility of the land. Regarding mung beans, he advised that after harvesting, when the stem begins to dry up, it should be plowed back into the field. Some farmers burn the stubble in their fields, thinking that it will act as fertilizer, but this belief is completely wrong. Burning stubble destroys the soil's fertility. The government has also imposed restrictions on this practice. Parimal Kumar Singh appealed to farmers to cultivate sesame and pulses with enthusiasm this year. The organization can provide good quality seeds for sesame farming and farmers can also deposit their seeds in seed banks.

District Agriculture Officer Kamal Kishor Kujur, while addressing farmers, thanked the government in New Delhi for supporting the cultivation of millets, pulses and oilseeds.

He inaugurated a booklet titled "Success Stories" with women farmer Subodhi Soren from Tulsitandan, and highlighted her ability to demonstrate her talent in remote rural areas. This is a matter of pride for the country. He assured the farmers present that they should cultivate pulses and oilseeds, and whatever support they need, they will receive from them. Finally, Mr. Vikas Arora thanked the farmers for their valuable time for the workshop.
